

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

PARC – Study design – protocol ‘sampling strategy’ participating studies PARC Aligned Studies (P4.1.1.1_Y1_GenHBMSurvey)

Partnership
FOR THE
Assessment
OF
Risks
FROM
Chemicals

Co-funded by
the European Union

This partnership has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under Grant Agreement No 101057014.

Introduction

The main goal of the PARC Aligned Studies (i.e. General Population HBM Survey) is to obtain HBM data that are comparable between European countries/regions (ref: [PARC general survey design revised final.pdf](#)). Important for this objective is to align the studies in all study phases and to collect a general population sample representative for that country or region according to predefined criteria. Although national level HBM studies are preferred, regional HBM studies can contribute when a national study is lacking and under specific conditions and criteria described in “[PARC general survey design revised final.pdf](#)”. In order to get a sample of participants representative of the general population of the country/region, a stratified clustered multi-stage design is most often used. This means that the selection is done in different stages. First, geographical units are defined in order to ensure the (spatial) distribution of participants within the country/region. Next, sampling units are defined within each geographical unit, i.e. the primary sampling unit (PSU) and the secondary sampling unit (SSU), and it is defined how participants are being sampled.

The representativeness of the sample depends on:

- the process that determines who can participate in the study (design, geographical coverage and sample size),
- the quality of the sampling frame (coverage: how well does the sampling frame cover the population of interest; e.g. when adolescents or children are recruited via schools individuals that are home-schooled are not included; when participants are selected from a national register homeless people are not included; or when participants are selected via occupational physicians unemployed people are not included)
- the response rate (particularly when biases are introduced, e.g., underrepresentation from individuals with lower socio-economic status).

This document proposes a design that allows to efficiently obtain a representative sample within a country/region. Previously conducted adolescent studies in Flanders (FLEHS) and the ALBANE study in France will be used to illustrate possible design and sampling.

Schematic representation of the recruitment strategy/design process:

1. Geographical strata selection

Proportionate geographical stratification: The geographical area for which the study aims to collect a representative sample is divided into non-overlapping geographical units covering the entire country/region. The N of participants to be included per strata is proportional to the population size of the strata.

2. First stage: Selection of PSU (cluster)

Weighted systematic sampling: chance of a PSU to be selected is proportional to its size.
For each strata: all PSU are ordered from large to small*

**The weight (size of the PSU) used in this procedure can be refined by including auxiliary information of the PSUs. e.g., One may consider giving these schools a higher chance of being selected via the systematic sampling procedure by multiplying their size by a positive factor proportional to the assessed efficiency.*

3. Second stage: Selection of SSU

Step 1: Geographical strata selection

Proportionate geographical stratification will be used to ensure good geographical coverage of the country/region. For stratification, the country/region is divided into strata (non-overlapping geographical units covering *the entire* country/region) and participants are sampled within each stratum so that there is no random sampling variation with respect to these geographical units. The stratification will prevent a stratum to be over- or underrepresented by chance. This may be the case in a random sample for a smaller stratum. Thus, in the first step, the geographical unit is to be defined.

The NUTS¹ regions can be used as strata. The choice of the NUTS level depends on the size of the country/region and the size of these NUTS units. Bigger countries can work with NUTS1 level and smaller countries with NUTS2 or NUTS3 level to ensure geographical coverage. Typically, 3 to 8 strata per region/country are used (for a study with a sample size of N = 150, this amounts to between 50 and 18 participants per stratum). It should be noted that the study area (region/country) is divided into strata so that the entire study area is covered. In other words, there is no selection of strata. One does have to decide how large the strata can be (e.g. choice between NUTS1, NUTS2, NUTS3¹). Of course, smaller geographical units can then be selected within each stratum; for example, selection of some municipalities or NUTS3 units within each NUTS1 stratum.

The precise number of participants per stratum is then determined and should be proportional to the population size of the stratum². Ideally, the size of the strata should be determined for the specific age group to be included in the study. For example, for studies targeting children aged 6-11 years, the total number of children to be sampled should be distributed proportionally across all strata based on the number of children aged 6-11 years living there. If this information is not available a proxy (e.g. the total population size) can be used. When an adequate sample is desired from both urban and rural populations, the strata can be further subdivided, for example based on the DEGURBA classification by EUROSTAT or the number of inhabitants per squared kilometer.

Example FLEHS. In previous adolescent studies in Flanders (FLEHS), stratification by provinces (NUTS2) was used. There are five Flemish provinces, for a total population of about 6.5 million. The number of residents per province (as a proxy for the adolescent population) on January 1st of the year that sampling started, was used as a basis to determine the number of participants per province. For a total study size of 300 participants, the number of participants per province (proportionate to the provinces population size) is given in the table below.

Province (NUTS2)	Number of inhabitants	Proportion of inhabitants	Number of participants
Antwerpen (BE21)	1 879 318	0.28	84
Limburg (BE22)	883 228	0.13	39
Oost-Vlaanderen (BE23)	1 533 876	0.23	69
Vlaams-Brabant (BE24)	1 163 186	0.17	51
West-Vlaanderen (BE25)	1 205 101	0.18	54
Total = Vlaams gewest (BE2)	6 664 709	1	300

¹ Make sure to use the latest NUTS classification i.e. [NUTS 2021 classification](#) valid from 1 January 2021.

² [Statistics | Eurostat \(europa.eu\)](#)

Example ALBANE: For the next HBM survey on general population in France (Albane, 2024-2026), a first stratification will be done at NUTS1 level, which will lead to divide the metropolitan territory by 13 areas (12 continental regions + Corse Island).

There are some specific areas which are considered as mandatory PSUs, basically the several arrondissements in Paris (20) located in Ile-de-France, Lyon (9) located in Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes and Marseille (16) which is located in and Provence-Alpes-Côtes-d’Azur regions. These zones are very high density areas that’s why the national statistic services consider those PSU as mandatory to include. The remaining number of PSU are proportional to the number of principal residences.

Province (NUTS1)	Number of principal residences¹	Mandatory PSU	Number of principal residences excluding mandatory PSU	Proportion of inhabitants	Number of PSUs without mandatory PSU	Total Number of PSUs
Ile-de-France (FR1)	5 256 723	20	4 118 964	0.150	18	38
Centre — Val de Loire (FRB)	1 167 463		1 167 463	0.043	5	5
Bourgogne-Franche-Comté (FRC)	1 299 484		1 299 484	0.047	6	6
Normandie (FRD)	1 500 917		1 500 917	0.055	7	7
Hauts-de-France (FRE)	2 561 385		2 561 385	0.094	11	11
Grand Est (FRF)	2 498 232		2 498 232	0.091	11	11
Pays de la Loire (FRG)	1 695 106		1 695 106	0.062	7	7
Bretagne (FRH)	1 549 542		1 549 542	0.057	7	7
Nouvelle-Aquitaine (FRI)	2 822 186		2 822 186	0.103	13	13
Occitanie (FRJ)	2 761 398		2 761 398	0.101	12	12
Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes (FRK)	3 606 379	9	3 336 872	0.122	15	24
Provence-Alpes-Côte d’Azur (FRL)	2 331 480	16	1 929 737	0.070	9	25
Corse (FRM)	149 985		149 985	0.005	1	1
Total France	29 200 280	45	27 391 271	1	122	167

Depending country by country it can be decided to exclude certain regions for feasibility reasons. E.g., in the previous French HBM campaign (ESTEBAN) Corse (FRM) was excluded, due to complex logistics and costs linked to sampling on the Isle Corse.

Step 2: First stage selection of PSU (cluster)

Next, within the strata (i.e. the geographical units covering the entire region/country), participants are often accessed in multiple stages. Multistage sampling is the best way to get access to the participants (adolescent, adults, ...). A direct selection of participants from e.g., a list of all eligible participants living in the stratum (single stage sampling) would be too expensive, because the spread and therefore the (traveling) costs would be too high. A cluster sampling design is more cost efficient. Therefore, a **multi-stage** design is advised, usually a two-stage design is used.

The primary sampling unit (PSU), i.e., the cluster, is the access point to recruit participants. In cluster sampling the population is assumed to be readily divided into naturally formed subgroups called clusters. For children or teenagers, the PSU could be the school; for adults (but also for children or teenagers), the PSU could be the municipality or group of municipalities. Recruitment via health centers, hospitals (newborns), child and family services, student support centers, etc. is possible and may have some practical advantages if blood samples need to be collected. But to obtain a representative sample, it is necessary to work with services that reach the entire (target) population and where no subgroups are excluded (e.g. healthy people, unemployed). Child and family services that routinely follow-up (almost) all young children thus are an option. Working via general practitioners may introduce bias if healthy people do not visit the general practitioner (regularly).

In general, the PSUs of a stratum vary in population size (e.g. large and small municipalities or large and small schools); therefore, it is advisable to build some rules into the random selection so that the sample contains PSUs ranging from large to small. This is achieved by a weighted systematic sampling where the chance for a PSU to be selected is proportional to its population size. By selecting PSUs through systematic sampling, there is little chance that only large cities/schools are included in the sample and result in an unrepresentative sample (on the condition that a sufficient number of PSUs are to be selected in the stratum).

Nowadays, most software packages have options to select a sample according to a complex multistage design that includes stratification, clustering, and unequal probabilities of selection; e.g. PROC SURVEYSELECT in SAS and package sampling in R.

Example to illustrate the weighted systematic sampling procedure:

Illustrative example on the selection of maternities (PSU) to recruit newborns in a stratum (e.g. province Antwerpen).

The number of newborns to be included for this stratum was proportionate to the number of deliveries (the 'population' size) and equals 50. To simplify the organization of the fieldwork, it was decided that 10 newborns would be included each time a maternity was selected. The 7 maternities present in the stratum (province Antwerpen) had different population sizes (i.e. number of deliveries). The 7 maternities are ordered (from small to large (A-G)) and expanded proportional to their size. Thus, in the graph below, each maternity is represented by a segment proportional to its size. The sums of the segments represent the total population size of the stratum (province Antwerpen). Next, this line is cut into 5 pieces (in this example). These 5 segments are superimposed on each other. Systematic sampling then amounts to drawing a random vertical line (the dashed brown line) by randomly selecting a number between 0-1, and each time this vertical line crosses a segment the corresponding maternity is selected, and 10 newborns are recruited. This results in a total of $5 \times 10 = 50$ newborns (the target for this stratum). In this procedure, the probability of selecting a maternity was proportional to its population size. Note that large maternities are represented by segments spanning multiple horizontal lines (e.g. maternities F and G in the example). The implication is that maternity G was selected twice and contributed 20 newborns to the stratum (province Antwerpen). By ranking the maternities according to their population size, a representation of smaller maternities (e.g maternity B) and large maternities (e.g. maternity G) is ensured.

Province (geographical strata)	PSUs (Maternities)	PSU size (deliveries/year)	Segment size/weight (proportional expansion)	Visualisation of weighted systematic sampling procedure
Antwerpen	Maternity A	30	0.23	
	Maternity B	60	0.46	
	Maternity C	62	0.47	
	Maternity D	80	0.61	
	Maternity E	100	0.76	
	Maternity F	120	0.92	
	Maternity G	200	1.53	

The weight (population size of the PSU) used in the weighted systematic sampling procedure can be refined by including auxiliary information of the PSUs. It is a fact that participation rate of people with lower educational level or social economic status tends to be lower. By increasing the probability of selecting specific PSUs, more participants in these subgroups will be invited to participate. This increases the likelihood of a proportional representation in the final sample (even with a lower response rate). Obviously, additional efforts will still have to be made during the fieldwork to convince enough adolescents/adults in these subgroups to participate in the study.

For example:

- by assigning a greater weight to maternities, where relatively more women of lower socio-economic status or migration background give birth, it is more likely that this group of pregnant women is adequately represented in the sample.
- schools that offer all levels of education (known to be associated with socio-economic characteristics of the students); or schools with a larger proportion of pupils from underprivileged families are 'more efficient' in obtaining a representative sample. One may consider giving these schools a higher chance of being selected via the systematic sampling procedure by multiplying their size by a positive factor proportional to the assessed efficiency.
- when municipalities are the PSU, information regarding the share of residents with a minimum wage can for example be used.

Within the stratum, the number of PSUs to be sampled is determined as a compromise between a good feasibility of the field work (hence, selection of a limited number of PSUs) and yet the need to allow enough variation in the sample (hence, selection of a sufficient number of PSUs). Non-response can also occur at the PSU level, a school/municipality not willing to participate. Therefore, for each PSU, a replacement PSU is to be selected from the list (also by systematic sampling).

Example FLEHS. Selection of schools. In the most recent adolescent study in Flanders (FLEHS), the PSUs are schools. It was decided to select two schools per province (so a total of 10 PSUs), one school in a rural area and one school in an urban area. Thus, the stratification was refined, and each province was further stratified in rural and urban municipalities (based on the number of inhabitants per squared kilometer). Hence, one school from the list of rural schools was randomly selected and one school from the list of urban schools was randomly selected. Schools were selected via weighted systematic sampling, and larger schools, schools with the three educational types and schools with relatively more underprivileged children had a higher chance to be selected.

Larger schools have a higher probability of being selected (probability to proportional to size). This probability is shown in column 5 in the table below. To account for a lower participation rate of adolescents with lower education levels or socio-economic status, the probability of selecting specific schools can be increased. The example illustrates this using an indicator “GOK” for the proportion of students from a lower social class. Column 6 in the table shows the percentage of GOK pupils (GOK stands for ‘gelijke onderwijskansen’ or ‘equal educational opportunities’) for each school. A student is a GOK student if the child's mother does not have a secondary school diploma or if the family receives an education allowance). For schools with more than 3 out of 4 students being GOK students (>75%), the school size can e.g. be increased 25%. The adjusted school sizes and selection probabilities are shown in columns 7 and 8.

In order to have sufficient geographical spread within a province, the two selected schools could not be located near each other. If two selected schools were located within a distance of less than 20 km, one school was removed, and a new school was randomly selected. If the randomly selected schools in one province all lack a specific education type, one school was removed and a new school is randomly selected, in order to get a mix of all possible education types in each province.

1. Provinces (geographical strata)	2. degree of urbanisation strata	3. PSUs (schools)	4. PSU size (school size)	5. Probability of selection	6. % GOK students	7. Adjusted PSU size (adjusted school size based on GOK, education types)	8. Adjusted Probability of selection
Antwerpen	Rural area/municipalities	School A	150 students	0.19	12%	150	0.19
		School B	180 students	0.23	21%	180	0.23
		School C	200 students	0.26	32%	200	0.26
		School D	250 students	0.32	17%	250	0.32
	Urban area/municipalities	School A	50 students	0.03	5%	50	0.03
		School B	120 students	0.08	25%	120	0.07
		School C	160 students	0.10	37%	200	0.10
		School D	210 students	0.14	52%	210	0.13
		School E	300 students	0.19	78%	375 (300 + 75)	0.23
		School F	300 students	0.19	24%	300	0.19
		School G	400 students	0.26	41%	400	0.25

Note: In this FLEHS example, a dichotomy for urbanization, i.e. urban versus rural, based on population density was used (for each municipality the number of inhabitants per km²). This pragmatic stratification was intended to bring the urban-rural distribution of the sample as close as possible to the population distribution. PARC recommends using the three-level DEGURBA categorization. Of course, the representation of these levels in the population should be looked at specifically for each country and the usefulness of the DEGURBA classification as a stratification factor should be evaluated.

Example ALBANE:

Among these NUTS 1 areas, a selection of Primary Sampling Units will be done by the national statistical service. PSUs are groups of municipalities that contains at least 2,500 main residential addresses. These groups are constituted to be as compact as possible in order to facilitate the survey fieldwork. The French metropolitan territory is divided in 5,155 PSUs. The probability of inclusion is calculated taking into account the number of principal residences among a PSU. Sociodemographic and geographical variables (e.g. density, incomes, population per age group) are taken into account to equilibrate the selected PSUs. Their number is not yet determined but will likely be between 150 and 170 PSUs for a total of 2,000 adults and 1,000 children recruited.

Step 3: second/third stage selection of SSU

So, at the first stage, PSUs (often a cluster such as a municipality, school, maternity) are drawn from the population of PSUs for each stratum (geographical unit). In the next stage, a sample is drawn from each PSU (multi-stage cluster sampling³). The secondary sampling unit (SSU) is the participant or a group of participants (if more than two-stage sampling is planned).

For example:

- Within the selected municipalities, a random selection of citizens can be made. This can be done using an alphabetically sorted registry list, using a fixed sampling interval and a random start; or the registry can be sorted by gender and age (implicit stratification).
- For adolescents, it is more practical to work with three-stage sampling. Within the schools (PSU), first a few classes (SSU) are selected at random and (all) pupils in these classes are invited to participate in the HBM study⁴.

The number of participants that can be included per PSU/SSU is largely determined by the feasibility of the fieldwork; the number of participants that can be examined on a daily basis by the fieldwork team, is after all, ceilinged. To optimize the organization of the fieldwork, and to reduce the time necessary to include sufficient participants it can be decided to exclude PSUs with too few eligible

³ In contrast to one-stage cluster sampling where all eligible participants of the sampled PSU are included in the survey. This is often not practical.

⁴ The advantage of clustered sampling, e.g. through schools or maternities, is mainly practical and budgetary because of lower travel costs. However, from a statistical point of view, clustered sampling is less efficient. The correlation (intracluster correlation coefficient or ICC) between observations belonging to the same cluster results in an increased standard error when estimating, for instance, a mean or proportion. If this correlation is strong, advanced statistical techniques such as mixed models or generalized estimating equations should be used.

In previous campaigns of FLEHS, the correlation between observations from the same maternity or secondary school was found to be low. Mothers who give birth in the same maternity live in a wider area. The same is true for schools, where students live in the wider vicinity (up to 20 km from the school). Note that the correlation between exposure for children from the same class could be strong if one were to select classes with a specific education, e.g. hairdresser. Or when sampling multiple members from the same household.

participants, from the sampling framework of a stratum. For example, schools with a very limited number of students can be excluded for the sampling framework.

The selection of schools in this example incorporates information about location (province and distance between schools), urbanization (rural/urban area), socio economic factors (educational level, the percentage of underprivileged children) and the size of the school to obtain a sample representative for the population.

Other scenarios are also possible:

- if at the moment of sampling information with respect to the age, gender and SES (or educational level as a proxy) is available for the population (via registries), implicit stratification can be used, for example when adults are sampled within municipalities or children within schools;
- when single-sex education occurs in a country, stratification by gender of (the children attending) the school may be considered;
- a good distribution of rural and urban participants can also be obtained by using the participant's place of residence (e.g. if recruited through municipalities).

Example ALBANE:

At a second step, from each selected PSU (groups of municipalities), participants are selected at individual level using a tax register, which contains individual information usable for stratification (sex, age, name of adults, incomes). Using age variable, the selection of participant can be controlled to ensure a minimal number of participants by age group (particularly for adolescents for whom participation rates are usually lowers).

Taking into account response rate

All candidates selected to participate in the project are contacted and invited to participate in the study. The number of subjects that is invited should be determined based on the response rate that is expected. In case a response rate of 20% is expected, the number of invited subjects is five times the aimed number. In their response (if they are willing to participate or not), candidates provide some personal information, on the inclusion and exclusion criteria of the study, but also about personal characteristics that during the fieldwork can be used to guarantee a representative sample. The information includes for instance age, sex, socio-economic status, residence and if they lived for five years or longer at this residence. A practical marker of socio-economic status is the education type of the participant. For children and teenagers, educational level of the parents is considered. Study participants that do not meet inclusion criteria are informed that they cannot participate in the study. The exclusion criteria for the recruitment phase for the studies participating in the PARC General Survey are described in "[PARC general survey design revised final.pdf](#)", i.e.:

- Institutionalized civilians (e.g., individuals residing in mental health institution, jail, ...).
- Individuals who did not provide written informed consent.
- Individuals who are not able to provide the requested samples.

- Individuals living in the country for a minimum period of time (1 to 3 years) (to be decided on at national level not EU level criteria).

Additional Points of attention for the planning of the sampling campaign

The distribution of participants by geographical location, age, gender and level of education in the final sample should be as close as possible to the population distribution. It is advisable to closely monitor how the different categories (e.g. girls/boys, age classes, rural/urban place of residence, ...) fill up during the study and to adjust if necessary. This can be done by calculating the targets for each criterion, and during the fieldwork count how many participants are already included/still need to be included to reach the targets by the end of the fieldwork. When planning the fieldwork, this information is available about the candidates/people willing to participate. So, numbers can be adjusted during recruitment by selecting among the candidate's participants that are needed to fill up the categories and refusing candidates from groups that are overrepresented.

A representative composition of the sample by socioeconomic status is important. For a sufficient participation in the lower socioeconomic classes, extra efforts should be made during the fieldwork (e.g., working with buddies, interpreters, extra information sessions...).

To account for seasonal effects, the fieldwork should be equally spread over all seasons. To avoid that seasonal effects are confounded with other effects good planning is needed, it should be avoided to do field work in all PSU's of the same geographical area in the same season, etc.

To account for participant drop-out, which may occur due to various reasons (e.g. not able to deliver the required sample volumes), one can consider to do little oversampling to reach the predefined target sample size.